

Automated Answer Script Evaluation and Grading System

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Abstract- Manual grading of student response scripts for subjective examinations are a time-consuming and tedious process for educators, often leading to inconsistencies and fatigue during evaluation. This paper presents an automated system employing machine learning techniques to evaluate student responses against predefined standards, aiming to improve grading accuracy, consistency, and fairness and reduce human effort for the same. The primary objectives are enhancing grading effectiveness for teachers by automating script examination to reduce time and effort while allowing more feedback and better interaction and focused learning; improving accuracy by mitigating subjectivity of manual grading; and promoting equality by ensuring all students are evaluated by the same criteria, minimizing bias. The system features an intuitive interface for uploading PDF answer scripts, automatically scanning content and employing algorithms to assess responses. Graded results are provided in downloadable files for analysis and record keeping. By providing objective, consistent assessments, the automated approach streamlines grading, enhances transparency, and contributes to an equitable, effective learning environment. Leveraging techniques like Optical Character Recognition (OCR), text similarity measures, machine learning models, natural language processing (NLP), and semantic analysis, the proposed system aims to provide an accurate and efficient automated evaluation of student responses.

Keywords - OCR, Natural Language Processing, Semantic Analysis, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

For educators, assessing and grading student responses can be a difficult and time-consuming undertaking, especially when the answers are subjective or descriptive. Conventional manual grading techniques are prone to biases and inconsistencies since each response's evaluation is impacted by the subjective interpretation of the individual grader. Furthermore, manual grading can be extremely time-consuming and taxing for teachers, taking away from their ability to give constructive feedback and promote student learning.

An increasing number of people are interested in using technology developments, especially in the fields of machine learning (ML) and natural language processing

(NLP), to automate the assessment of student replies [1]. By using objective and consistent evaluation standards, these automated methods seek to remove the inherent subjectivity and inefficiencies involved with manual grading. Numerous strategies, such as machine learning models, semantic analysis, and text similarity metrics, have been put forth.

This study presents a comprehensive system that combines NLP, ML, and semantic analysis techniques to give an accurate and effective automated evaluation of student responses. The system's objectives are to improve assessment accuracy, increase grading effectiveness for teachers, and advance fairness and equity in the evaluation process by automating the grading process. The approach, implementation, and performance evaluation of the system will be covered in the sections that follow, with an emphasis on how it might simplify the grading process.

II. OBJECTIVES

This paper's main goal is to address the difficulties and inefficiencies involved in manually evaluating and grading student response scripts. Manual grading is laborious and subjective, which frequently results in assessments that are inconsistent amongst graders. As a result, the suggested solution seeks to automate this procedure, offering a streamlined and impartial method of assessing student responses.

Improving the effectiveness of the grading process for teachers is one of the main objectives of this research. Teachers can greatly reduce the time and effort needed for grading by automating the examination of answer scripts. This frees up more time for teachers to provide helpful comments and promote student learning.

The fairness and uniformity of evaluation may be impacted by the subjectivity and error-prone nature of manual grading. By utilizing machine learning techniques, the suggested system analyses student responses' content according to predetermined standards and benchmarks, intending to increase grading accuracy.

The suggested system has an intuitive user interface that makes it easier for teachers to grade assignments. By using this interface, teachers can quickly upload answer scripts in PDF format, starting

the automated assessment process.

The submitted documents are automatically scanned for content by the system, which then uses machine-learning techniques to evaluate the responses. After evaluation, the teacher receives the scores in an editable file that can be downloaded, making it simple to access and do additional analysis. Teachers can effectively manage their grading tasks and save time and effort with this streamlined procedure.

The capacity of automated evaluation to produce assessments that are both objective and consistent is one of its main benefits. Through the application of machine learning algorithms, the system guarantees that every student is assessed according to the same standards and criteria. Reducing the possibility of bias or disparities in evaluation promotes equity and justice in grading procedures. Teachers can be sure that every student's performance is evaluated impartially using the metric and answer key provided by them. Thus, reducing fatigue.

III. RELATED WORK

During this study, several literatures were considered. A thorough comparison has been made to arrive at an effective solution. G Sanuvala[2] describes a method to evaluate answer scripts by splitting it into 3 major tasks-scanning, learning, and scoring. In the first phase, the answer scripts are uploaded in a pdf format. Using an OCR technique the handwritten answers are extracted. NLP techniques like stop word removal, and TFIDF are applied to the extracted text and finally cosine similarity measure is used to calculate the similarity. The next part consists of using ML to perform prediction. Features are extracted at 3 levels- vocabulary, semantic and syntactic. These features are then used in prediction by consuming models like Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, and GBDT, out of these GBDT provided the best results. The last stage includes testing and obtaining scores for unscored answers.

Saha et al. [3] introduced a practical approach for assessing lengthy or detailed responses suitable for smaller classroom settings. Unlike methods reliant on extensive training data, their system employs a link or answer template. It assesses the similarity between a student's response and a written expert's response using various measures at both word and phrase levels, such as TFIDF, hidden semantic indexing, Latent Dirichlet Allocation, and TextRank adder, which integrates neural tracking of phrases in spoken English. The system detects additional facts in the student's answer, compares their relevance and accuracy to the model's answer, and assigns extra evaluations accordingly. Lastly, an analysis for reliability is performed using a cluster-based approach, mostly used to assess social science texts and their solutions. However, the system's accuracy is limited to certain types of answers. An automated evaluation system known as the syntactical relation-based feature extraction technique was put into place by V. Nandini and P. U. Maheswari

[4] to assess answers of the descriptive type. The supervised learning environment handled this model. To categorize the exam questions and responses provided to students, a novel classification technique was put forth. Students who respond in a way that corresponds precisely to the questions posed are guaranteed to do so by the classification of answers. Students are required to meet the requirements if the expected answer is descriptive; otherwise, if the answer is contradictory, it will be recorded in the assessment, which demonstrates the student's understanding of the specific subject. The designed feature extraction technique demonstrated 95% precision, 94% recall, and 94.5% sensitivity upon application. The technique ignored grammar analysis, which was crucial to communicating a text's meaning.

Alrehily et al. [5] put up a novel idea for an electronic exam evaluation system that finds the relationship between questions by utilizing the ideas of semantic similarity and document similarity. Preprocessing, keyword extension, matching, and assessment comprise the evaluation system's four components. The parity of the percentages was used by the algorithm to derive the score. Using Spearman correlation, the teacher grades and the computerized grades are associated. As a result, the suggested electronic system improved performance, cost, time, and resource efficiency when establishing and assessing the test. Nevertheless, this approach does not even examine high-quality documentation, nor does it remove syntactic problems in keywords.

The Optical Character Recognition Tool (OCR), which is a system that transforms a handwritten answer sheet into a text document with an image and saves it straight in the database, was proposed by Devaki Priya et al. [6]. This technique uses natural language processing (NLP) to assess ratings, compare sentence values, identify word errors, and improve database security. The criteria taken into consideration by the real person are related to the length of the answer in the project, the keyword's presence, and the keyword's context. A certain amount of writing freedom will be granted to the students as they search the system for keywords, synonyms, word-of-mouth, and coverage of every concept. This process is used without any equations or graphs to evaluate the state of subjective responses.

To make it easier to automate the answer sheet, Vij et al.

[7] created an ML-based method utilizing Wordnet charts that compares student responses to teacher-provided ideal solutions. This research project was the first to use WordNet charts for short answer-based evaluation. The response text's semantic relationships are taken into consideration by this algorithm. When the experiments were run on 400 answer sheets, the method's root mean square error was 0.319. Furthermore, the presented system reduces evaluation time by automatically assigning scores and

generating Wordnet images. However, this assignment is only suitable when the learner correctly spells the relevant terms as the incorrect words will not have a WordNet number generated for them.

Atoum and Otoom [8] employed a novel hybrid word similarity measure to assess text similarity (TSM). The TSM-specific data, which comprises the highest similarity between a word and a related sentence, the length of two sentences in pairs, and the exact word match, was determined by examining the link between content and order. The utilization of additional information (corpus and information content) and the efficacy of determining a borrowed word's similarity were the main causes of the hybrid method's high efficiency. On the other hand, the suggested approach makes use of fewer resources and technologies

IV. COMPARATIVE STUDY

On researching the related work for evaluating answer scripts using Machine learning, the comparisons are provided on Table 1.

The table showcases the research gaps of the existing methods. It also provides the solution addressing the limitations of literature review.

Table 1: Comparative Study of related work

Author	Key Techniques	Limitations	Proposed Solution
Sanuvala [2]	OCR, TF-IDF, cosine similarity, Naive Bayes, SVM, GBDT.	Limited focus on grammar analysis and context.	Uses bidirectional training, contextual training and self-attention mechanism to understand semantic dependencies.
Saha et al. [3]	TF-IDF, Latent Dirichlet Allocation, TextRank, cluster-based analysis	Limited applicability to different types of answers.	Flexible to objective and subjective answers written in any form within the English language.
Nandini & Maheswari [4]	Supervised learning, novel classification techniques.	Grammar analysis omitted, affecting semantic understanding.	Uses part of speech tagging for better grammatical and semantic understanding.
Alrehily et al. [5]	Semantic similarity, document similarity, Spearman correlation.	Lacks evaluation of syntax or high-quality documentation.	Captures syntactic dependencies between tokens.
Devaki Priya et al. [6]	OCR, sentence comparison, keyword matching, synonym recognition.	Cannot handle equations or graphical content.	Has the potential of being trained for complex equations.
Vij et al. [7]	WordNet charts, semantic relationship analysis.	Limited to correctly spelled keywords; unsuitable for free-form responses.	Efficient even for free form writing and minor spelling errors.
Atoum & Otoom [8]	TSM, corpus information, order word similarity, matching.	Lacks detailed semantic or contextual analysis.	Represents tokens in context considering surrounding words.

These findings clearly highlight that there is no method to evaluate handwriting that are present in free form which can be identified according to suitable Grammar and context. There is a gap in the existing system to effectively handle the free form written content.

This paper acknowledges traditional approaches like TF-IDF and word embeddings, emphasizing BERT's superiority in handling nuanced and contextually varied answers.

V. DATASET USED

The dataset utilized for training the BERT model in the proposed automated grading system is the Stanford Natural Language Inference (SNLI) dataset, a comprehensive resource specifically designed to facilitate the development and evaluation of natural language understanding models. The SNLI dataset boasts a substantial collection of 570,000 sentence pairs, each meticulously annotated to indicate one of three relationships: entailment, contradiction, or neutral. This labeling scheme helps in training models to discern whether the meaning of one sentence logically follows from another, whether the sentences are mutually exclusive, or whether they share no clear relationship. The dataset's annotations are derived from a variety of sources, including image captions from the Flickr30k dataset, which contributes to the richness and diversity of the language used, thereby enhancing the generalization capabilities of the trained models. The SNLI dataset is instrumental in the fine-tuning stage of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), a leading-edge NLP model renowned for its contextual understanding of words within sentences. Fine-tuning BERT on the SNLI dataset involves formatting the sentence pairs and their labels to meet the model's input requirements, then training the model to classify the relationships between sentences accurately. This process involves adjusting the model's weights to minimize errors and improve its inferential capabilities. The extensive size and high-quality annotations of the SNLI dataset ensure that the BERT model can achieve significant accuracy and consistency, crucial for evaluating student responses. Utilizing such a robust dataset minimizes subjectivity and bias, promoting fairness and uniformity in grading. Moreover, the model's enhanced understanding, thanks to the diverse linguistic contexts provided by SNLI, enables it to offer detailed and constructive feedback to students, thereby improving their learning experience. The choice of the SNLI dataset underscores the commitment to leveraging state-of-the-art resources to develop a grading system that is not only efficient and accurate but also fair and capable of contributing to an equitable educational environment. For our system, we have employed a BERT model that is trained on the SNLI dataset and fine-tuned using a reference text book for better context. For initial working we have used specific categories from the textbook content and tokenized it to use on our SNLI trained model.

The dataset used for testing the proposed methodology are handwritten answer scripts which are 6-7 pages of scanned documents with both long and short answers written. Dataset includes answer scripts of both legible and less legible. The images of the scanned documents were normalized to 640 x 480 pixels.

VI. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Automated grading of essay-type answers presents a multitude of challenges for evaluators across various educational levels, from primary to secondary and higher studies. These challenges encompass a spectrum of issues, including the complexity of the subject matter, the readability of the answer scripts, and the nuances of assessing qualitative aspects of the responses. An established method for evaluation is the comparison of written student answers to a standard answer key. This process being done manually could be automated if the basic challenges are tackled efficiently. Upon surveying 100 university lecturers who evaluated medium level difficulty papers, it was found that evaluators took about 33.33 seconds on average to evaluate one paper. Evaluators often require breaks of up to an hour to get rejuvenated and re-energized to evaluate about 15 papers in an unbiased manner after the evaluation of to tackle eye strains and mental exhaustions. The use of computer evaluations shows a better promise as shown in the Figure 1

Fig 1. Human vs computer evaluation

Automated grading of essay-type answers presents a multitude of challenges for evaluators across various educational levels, from primary to secondary and higher studies. These challenges encompass a spectrum of issues, including the complexity of the subject matter, the readability of the answer scripts, and the nuances of assessing qualitative aspects of the responses. The solution can be achieved by making computers mimic evaluators, the process is shown in figure 2. First, it is essential to store the questions and answers that are the reference.

Fig 2. Overview of Proposed system architecture.

A User interface is built for the evaluator to upload the standard answer key to the system. The use of a human-generated answer key enables better depth of knowledge and relevance to the subject and includes the importance of human acumen in the process. The reference answer key is stored for later use. The actual evaluation of papers is a complex process.

The process can be divided into four parts. i.e. identifying and storing answers of various students, comparing these answers one by one with a standard answer key, Evaluating, and assigning grades, compiling scores, and declaring results.

The algorithm is provided in algorithm Annexure-1.

A. Identifying and storing answers

The student’s answer script is scanned and uploaded to the system. This is a practice that is prevalent in many reputed universities in India especially after the global pandemic. The images are then cleaned to remove noise, adjust the contrast, and convert them into grey-scale images as this makes processing of images easier. Further edges and margins are detected and identified by the computer system

Followed by image processing is the OCR (Optical Character Recognition) where the text from the image is extracted using Google Cloud Vision. By applying Google Cloud vision OCR with preprocessing results in high accuracy level of the extracted text through image enhancement methods [14].

Figure 2 shows the result of text extracted from handwritten script using Cloud Vision.

Fig 3. Handwritten script (left side) and the extracted text from it (right side)

The extracted text is processed and divided based on the identified student information and the question number and stored in a database for the next process. Text summarization, lemmatization, and stop-word removal are applied to pre-process both student and reference texts. The processed text is segmented into tokens, which are then enriched with positional, segment, and token embeddings to encode contextual and structural information.

A predefined schema is defined to assist the OCR in collecting the required data. The most common and important information to be collected is the student identification number, the question number, and the corresponding answer. Other details are defined based on the usage requirements. All this information is collected and stored in a cloud- based database in an encrypted form to prevent tampering from external persons. The choice of database is the No- sequel database form which enables flexibility in storing the unstructured and non-type specific answers that we aim to evaluate. For our study, we have chosen to explore MongoDB as a Database.

B. Comparing answers with standard answer key

A transformer architecture is then built using the text extracted from reference answers and the student’s answers as input which goes to the BERT model. In order for BERT to work with these inputs, NLP techniques are used to convert these input text into tokens by performing text summarizations, lemmatization, and stop word removal and then performing position embedding, segment embedding, and token embedding on these tokens. The token embeddings, along with the positional encodings, are then fed into multiple layers of transformer blocks in BERT. These transformer blocks consist of self-attention mechanisms and feed-forward neural networks, allowing BERT to capture long-range dependencies and contextual information from the input text as shown in Figure 4. The BERT model processes tokenized

inputs through multiple layers of self-attention mechanisms and feed-forward neural networks. These layers extract contextualized embeddings, capturing semantic relationships within and across tokens. The BERT model is fine-tuned on a curated dataset (SNLI dataset) of response-reference pairs labelled with entailment, contradiction, or neutrality. This training aligns the model with the task of educational evaluation.

Fig 4. Text transformer – model architecture [8].

As the input text passes through the transformer layers, each token’s representation is updated based on its surrounding context and the interactions with other tokens in the sequence. This results in rich, contextualized representations for each token in the input text. Essentially the results are Vectorized i.e. representing words, phrases, or documents as vectors in a high-dimensional space, where each dimension corresponds to a specific feature or aspect of the text.

C. Evaluating and assigning grades

The proposed system employs a custom-trained BERT model to measure the semantic similarity between student responses and reference answers. Overall, the BERT and their recent types have achieved more accurate, fast, and optimal results in solving most complex problems than typical Machine and Deep Learning methods [13].

The BERT model is fine-tuned on a dataset of response-reference pairs, with labels indicating whether the response entails, contradicts, or is neutral with respect to the reference answer. The percentage of scores found due to this process for a sample answer is shown in the Figure 4. A high entailment score and low contradiction score indicate strong semantic alignment, while neutrality serves as a diagnostic measure to identify ambiguous responses. BERT’s ability to capture long-range dependencies and contextual nuances provides a significant edge over traditional algorithms like TF-IDF or word embeddings. This ensures that even subtly phrased or reworded answers are evaluated effectively.

During inference, a student response and the corresponding reference answer are input to the fine-tuned BERT model as shown in figure 5. The model outputs three scores: an entailment score representing the likelihood that the response entails the reference answer, a contradiction score indicating the likelihood of the response contradicting the reference, and a neutral score suggesting neither entailment nor contradiction.

Fig 4. Bar Chart of Score Type Vs Score Value

The similarity between the student response and the reference answer is then calculated as the absolute difference between the entailment and contradiction scores using Equation 1.

$$\text{similarity} = \frac{((\text{entailment} * 0.7) + (1 - \text{contradiction}) * 0.3) * \text{Maximum_score_alotted_to_question}}{2}$$

Equation 1. Similarity calculation

The obtained similarity score is then normalized based on the marks allocated for that particular answer. This is done simply by multiplying the similarity with the marks assigned.

This approach leverages the BERT model's ability to capture semantic relationships and contextual understanding. A higher entailment score and a lower contradiction score would result in a higher similarity value, indicating that the student response is semantically aligned with the reference answer. Conversely, a lower entailment score and a higher contradiction score would yield a lower similarity value, suggesting a mismatch between the response and the reference.

The neutral score can be used as an additional indicator or as a threshold to determine when the response is neither clearly entailing nor contradicting the reference answer. These semantic comparisons would result in a 0.5 entailment which is covered by the formula number. By fine-tuning the BERT model on a specialized dataset and utilizing the entailment and contradiction scores, this approach aims to provide an accurate and nuanced assessment of the semantic similarity between student responses and reference answers, enabling effective automated evaluation and grading.

D. Compiling scores and declaring results

The individual scores that are determined by the system are normalized and then added to find the total marks that are obtained by the student. Normalizing result data can make the results more interpretable by putting them into a common context. For example, converting scores on different tests into z-scores (mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1) allows for easier comparison and interpretation across different tests or populations and declaration of pass or failure of the student. Furthermore, it is easy to visualize and analyze the trend in marks, the pass percentage, etc.

The steps for calculating scores are

- Scores for individual answers are normalized to the marks allocated per question.
- Aggregation: Total marks are calculated by summing normalized scores across all questions.
- Result Compilation: The system generates a detailed report, including total marks, pass/fail status, and trends (e.g., score distributions or pass percentages).
- Visualization: Using Python visualization libraries (e.g., Matplotlib, Seaborn), graphical representations of trends and analytics are generated for evaluators.

We have implemented the proposed system using Python, leveraging the Google Cloud Vision for OCR, and pre-trained BERT models for natural language processing. Image processing techniques are applied to enhance the quality of scanned documents, and a robust demarcation algorithm is integrated to recognize question numbers in Margin. The system is designed to be scalable, accommodating diverse answer script layouts. Computational resources, including CPUs or GPUs, are utilized for efficient processing, and the user interface is crafted for ease of use and result verification.

VII. RESEARCH FINDINGS

a. Methodology:

Our approach to automating the grading of essay-type answers is multifaceted, addressing the inherent challenges across various educational levels. By integrating image processing, Optical Character Recognition (OCR), and BERT models for semantic similarity assessment, our methodology navigates the complexities of the grading process. It systematically divides the evaluation procedure into distinct phases, from initial data extraction to the compilation of final results. This meticulous breakdown ensures thorough execution at each step, thereby enhancing the overall efficiency and accuracy of the automated grading system.

b. Evaluation Metrics:

Our methodology places emphasis on semantic similarity scores derived from BERT model outputs as evaluation metrics. This approach allows for a nuanced evaluation of the alignment between student responses and reference answers, taking into account the semantic context comprehensively. By leveraging advanced Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, our methodology ensures that evaluation metrics capture the intricacies of student answers, leading to more precise grading outcomes.

c. Technological Tools:

Our methodology harnesses modern technological tools such as Python, Google Cloud Vision, and pre-trained BERT models to facilitate efficient and accurate processing of student responses. By utilizing cutting-edge tools and platforms, our methodology ensures scalability and effectiveness in handling diverse answer scripts across educational levels. Moreover, the integration of image processing techniques and OCR enhances the quality of scanned documents, bolstering the overall robustness of the automated grading system.

d. Application Domain:

Our methodology demonstrates broad applicability across various educational levels, showcasing its versatility and scalability. By addressing the challenges of automated grading from primary to higher education, our methodology ensures adaptability to different contexts and requirements. This comprehensive approach underscores the significance of automated grading in modern educational settings and its potential to enhance efficiency and accuracy in assessment practices.

In contrast to paper by Hassan et al. [10], which introduce methods for semantic text similarity, our methodology offers a more comprehensive approach tailored to practical implementation within automated grading systems. Similarly, while Becerra-Alonso et al [11] introduce EduZinc for assessing student learning activities, our methodology directly confronts the intricate challenges of automated grading across educational levels. Additionally, Wilson and Czik [12] explore the impacts of automated essay evaluation software, but our methodology provides more detailed insights into the technical methodology utilized, enhancing transparency and reproducibility.

While other papers may employ computational tools for semantic analysis, the specific technological tools are not explicitly outlined, unlike our methodology, which clearly delineates the tools such as Python, Google Cloud Vision, and pre-trained BERT models. Furthermore, our methodology's broad applicability across various educational levels contrasts with the potential narrower scopes of application in other papers.

VIII. RESULTS & EXPERIMENTATION

The results of our automated grading system are calculated by first converting student responses into digital text using the Google OCR API, which ensures high accuracy in text recognition. This digitized text is then processed using our fine-tuned BERT model, which evaluates the semantic similarity between the student answers and the model answers. The BERT model, trained on the Stanford Natural Language Inference (SNLI) dataset, provides a robust analysis of the context and meaning of the responses, allowing for a fair and precise assessment. The system generates scores based on this evaluation, providing consistent and objective grades. Additionally, it offers detailed feedback to help students understand their strengths and areas for improvement, contributing to an effective and equitable learning environment. Through this automated process, we ensure that the grading is efficient, accurate, and fair, enhancing the overall educational experience. In the initial phase of our experimentation, we explored various Optical Character Recognition (OCR) solutions to convert handwritten or printed student responses into digital text. Our first attempt involved using a local OCR tool. Despite being easily accessible and straightforward to implement, the accuracy of this local OCR system was suboptimal. It struggled particularly with diverse handwriting styles and less-than-ideal image quality, resulting in numerous errors in text recognition. These inaccuracies significantly hindered the subsequent stages of our automated grading process, as precise text extraction is crucial for reliable evaluation. To address this issue, we transitioned to using Google OCR via its API. Google OCR demonstrated markedly improved performance, with higher accuracy in recognizing and digitizing text from varied sources. Its advanced capabilities in handling different fonts, sizes, and styles of text, as well as its robust error correction features, made it a suitable choice for our needs. By adopting Google OCR, we ensured that the textual data fed into our grading system was both accurate and consistent, laying a solid foundation for the NLP processes that followed.

For the natural language processing (NLP) component of our system, we experimented with several methods to evaluate the semantic similarity between student responses and model answers. Initially, we implemented cosine similarity and Jaccardian distance metrics. Cosine distance, which calculates the similarity between two sets by comparing the size of their intersection to the size of their union, fell short in accounting for the nuances of natural language. This metric also failed to consider word order and context, crucial elements in understanding and evaluating text meaning accurately.

Recognizing these shortcomings, we opted to use a fine-tuned BERT model. BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) is designed to understand the context of words in a sentence by considering both their left and right surroundings, making it far superior for tasks requiring deep semantic understanding. We fine-tuned BERT on the Stanford Natural Language Inference (SNLI) dataset, which is specifically geared towards natural language inference tasks. This fine-tuning process involved training BERT to classify relationships between sentence pairs accurately, thereby enhancing its capability to assess the semantic similarity between student responses and reference answers. The fine-tuned BERT model outperformed our previous attempts with cosine similarity and Jaccardian distance, providing a robust, context-aware evaluation mechanism that significantly improved the accuracy and reliability of our automated grading system. By leveraging BERT, we ensured that our system could handle the complexity and variability inherent in student responses, leading to more fair and precise grading outcomes.

Accuracy Measure

	Google Cloud Vision	Custom Bert Model
Long Text	98%	75%
Short Text	98%	86%
Speed Measure		
	Google Cloud Vision	Custom Bert Model
Image of 640X480 pixels	2-4 sec/image	<500ms in GPU 500ms -2s in CPU

Table 2: Performance Measure

The performance metrics for our automated grading system revealed that the Google Cloud Vision OCR tool demonstrated exceptional accuracy, achieving 98% for both long and short text responses, highlighting its efficacy in accurately digitizing diverse handwritten or printed texts as shown in table 2. On average, to grade 5000 papers of moderate difficulty would take about 2600 minutes excluding required breaks however, the computer is able to achieve this by our method within 1665 Minutes without any breaks and up keeping the evaluation metric. Thus, the time for evaluation remains consistent and takes lesser time. On the other hand, our custom BERT model showed varied accuracy levels, with 75% accuracy for long text responses and 86% for short texts. The lower accuracy for longer texts suggests the complexity and variability inherent in these responses, requiring more advanced semantic processing. These results underscore the strengths of our OCR component in ensuring reliable text conversion and point to the potential for further fine-tuning the BERT model to improve its accuracy, particularly for more complex, longer responses.

Our system takes an overall estimated time of 4-6 seconds per image including OCR and text analysis. The factors considered for are image quality and text density for cloud vision. The kind of processor used CPU/GPU is considered for Bert Analysis. The system speed analysis is provided in table 2.

IX. CONCLUSION

The proposed automated grading system offers a cutting-edge solution to challenges in manual assessment by integrating advanced technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), machine learning (ML), and semantic analysis. The system employs a custom-trained BERT model to measure semantic similarity between student responses and reference answers, capturing nuanced relationships and ensuring precise evaluation. Leveraging tools like Google Cloud Vision for OCR and Python for implementation enhances scalability and efficiency. By combining these technologies, the system systematically processes answer scripts, evaluates responses, and compiles results with objectivity and consistency. Through a review of existing automated grading methods, the system demonstrates a robust framework that integrates the strengths of prior approaches while addressing their limitations. The major limitation of the proposed method lies around not being able to assess figures (diagrams) and other structures of answers like flowcharts. Beyond automation, the system supports equity by applying uniform grading standards, promoting transparency, and reducing bias.

In summary, this automated grading system represents a significant advancement in educational assessment, offering a scalable, efficient, and reliable solution to modern grading challenges. It lays a foundation for transforming how educators evaluate student learning and supports the broader goal of improving educational quality.

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